

The Examination of The Impact of Teacher Self-Efficacy on Powerlessness in Work Alienation

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Abstract

Keywords:

Teacher self-
efficacy,
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School
management.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of teachers' and principals' self-efficacy and work self-efficacy on powerlessness dimension of work alienation. As the data gathering tool, "Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale", which was developed by Tschannen-Mooran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001) and translated into Turkish by Çapa and her colleagues (2005) and "Work Alienation Scale" developed by Elma (2003) were used. Population consists of 1736 teachers and principals working at elementary schools in the city center of Kayseri. 326 persons from this group participated in the study. In the research, the impact of teachers' self-efficacy on powerlessness was studied. R language and Bibliometrix were used to investigate the position of this study in academic research on the same topic in the Scopus Index in the last five years (2019-2023).

Öğretmenlerin Öz Yeterliliklerinin İşe Yabancılaşma Güçsüzlük Boyutu Üzerindeki Etkisinin İncelenmesi

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Öğretmen öz-
yeterliliği,
İşe yabancılaşma,
Güçsüzlük,
Bibliyometri,
Okul yönetimi

Bu çalışmanın amacı, öğretmenlerin ve yöneticilerin öz-yeterliliklerinin işe yabancılaşmanın güçsüzlük boyutlu üzerindeki etkilerini araştırmaktır. Veri toplama aracı olarak Tschannen-Mooran ve Woolfolk Hoy (2001) tarafından geliştirilen ve Çapa ve arkadaşları (2005) tarafından Türkçeye çevrilen "Öğretmen Öz-Yeterlilik Ölçeği" ve Elma (2003) tarafından geliştirilen "İşe Yabancılaşma Ölçeği" kullanılmıştır. Elma (2003) tarafından geliştirilen "İşe Yabancılaşma Ölçeği" kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın evrenini Kayseri il merkezindeki ilköğretim okullarında görev yapan 1.736 öğretmen ve okul yöneticisi oluşturmaktadır. Bu gruptan 326'sı araştırmaya katılmıştır. Çalışmanın, Scopus Endeksi'nde aynı konudaki son beş yılda (2019-2023) yapılan akademik araştırmalar içerisindeki konumunu tespit etmek için R dili ile uyumlu çalışan Bibliometrix Biblioshy kullanılmıştır.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of self-efficacy was first introduced by Bandura within the context of “cognitive behavioral change” in 1977 (Bikmaz, 2002). It is known that self-efficacy functions like a thermometer, influencing and altering individuals’ working and learning processes (Dembo, 2004). Research suggests that self-efficacy enhances performance through the use of personal goals, reactions, and analytic strategies, and it significantly impacts individual motivation (Gerçek et al., 2006; Bilgen et al., 2018). Studies related to education indicate that self-efficacy perceptions are crucial in determining students’ motivations (Dembo, 2004; Seker et al., 2023).

One of the key concepts related to the identity of the teaching profession is teacher self-efficacy. By its very nature, teaching is a complex, dynamic, non-linear, and ill-defined problem that needs to be solved (Bray-Clark & Bates, 2003). Research shows that one of the strongest determinants of a teacher's impact on students is their belief that their actions can make a difference. This belief is closely related to teachers' self-efficacy (Slavin, 2006). A perceived sense of self-efficacy helps teachers understand how much effort they need to put in to achieve their goals and how they can cope with the challenges they face. Individuals can develop a range of strategies to overcome these challenges, and their beliefs about the effectiveness and success of these strategies are linked to self-efficacy (Pajares & Schunk, 2001).

Teacher self-efficacy is not about teachers' success or the quality of their teaching (Goddard, Hoy, & Woolfolk-Hoy, 2000), but rather about their responses to questions regarding the planning and implementation of instructional tasks and actions (Goddard, Hoy, & Woolfolk-Hoy, 2004). Therefore, teacher self-efficacy can be defined as the belief in their ability to effectively carry out the teaching-learning process, create desired behaviors in students, and bring about necessary behavior changes (Arslan and Duru, 2022: 2136).

While Weisskopf (1996) defines alienation as “the oppression of certain aspects of human nature,” Elma (2003) describes it as “employees finding their jobs meaningless, failing to get satisfaction from workplace relationships, feeling alone, inadequate, and weak, losing hope for the future, and perceiving themselves as a cog in the wheel.”

Burnout and alienation from school significantly impact pre-service teachers in the field of education, leading to negative attitudes towards school, the education they receive, the profession they are about to undertake, learning new information, their environment, and even themselves. When examining studies on the relationship between alienation and burnout among university students, only one study (Tümkiye and Cavusoglu, 2016; Seker et al., 2022) was found to address these two variables together in the field of education.

Erjem (2015) found that teachers exposed to certain marginalizing situations (such as overcrowded classrooms, heavy course loads, lack of teaching materials, administrative problems, and rigid curricula) experience alienation in some but not all dimensions.

In empirical studies, the alienation dimensions conceptualized by Seeman (1959) are most frequently used. Seeman (1959) examined alienation in five categories based on individuals' self-perceptions and behaviors: Powerlessness, Meaninglessness, Normlessness, Isolation, and Self-estrangement. Powerlessness, the focus of our study, can be described as “people’s loss of control over events and their feeling that they cannot reflect their true selves in these events” (Başaran, 2004).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. The Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of self-efficacy and work self-efficacy of teachers and principals working at schools affiliated to The Ministry of National Education in Kayseri/ Turkey on powerlessness dimension of work alienation.

2.2. The Importance of the Research

There are many studies in the literature about the academic self-efficacy of teachers and work alienation. However, in the literature reviews conducted within the scope of the research, there were no

studies investigating the self-efficacy of teachers and the dimension of powerlessness of work alienation.

2.3. Sample and Research Model

For the bibliometric analysis of academic articles in the Scopus index, the R programming language and the Bibliometrix Biblioshiny plugin available for this language were used. The results obtained by questioning self-efficacy and job alienation in the Scopus index were visualized in Biblioshiny. A search of the Scopus index revealed no studies examining teacher self-efficacy and alienation from 1998 through 2023.

Bibliometrix is a powerful tool for analyzing academic literature and was developed in the R programming language. The tool is used to determine research trends by conducting bibliographic analysis of scientific publications, evaluate research results and take into account various scientific indicators Bibliometrics gives researchers the opportunity to analyze and understand the scientific literature in more depth. It is mainly used for the following purposes (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017).:

1. Identify research trends: Determine which topics are popular and which are studied more.
2. Evaluation of learning achievement: Evaluation of individual or institutional learning achievement using indicators such as citation numbers and publication.
3. Scientific Collaboration Analysis: Determine which researchers or institutions are actively collaborating.
4. Measuring Scientific Impact: Understanding which publications and authors are the most influential in this field.
5. Thanks to these analyses, bibliography allows researchers to better understand the literature and guide future research.

Necessary data was collected by face to face surveys since it has a high rate of answering and allows to ask a number of questions (Yalçın, Alparslan and Şeker, 2021). It was aimed to reach 500 persons out of 1736 that consist of teachers and principals working at elementary schools affiliated to The Ministry of National Education in the city center of Kayseri by simple random sampling in 2023. 483 persons, however, were reached due to time limitations and teachers' busy schedules. 326 surveys were included in the research as a result of validity and reliability analyses. Since surveys were applied according to the appointments arranged by the schools, the completion of surveys took 6 months.

Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale consisting of 24 questions that was developed by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001) and translated into Turkish by Çapa and her colleagues (2005) were used in order to measure the self-efficacy levels of teachers forming the sample of the research. The scale is formed by 3 dimensions, namely student participation, teaching strategies and classroom management. It is a 5-point Likert scale.

Work Alienation of Elementary School Teachers Scale" developed by Elma (2003) was used in order to measure powerlessness levels of teachers in work alienation. It is formed by 4 sub dimensions as powerlessness, meaninglessness, isolation and alienation to school and a 5-point Likert scale.

3. RESULTS

We compared studies in which the concepts "self-efficacy and work" and "self-efficacy and alienation" were considered together in scientific articles in the scopus index over the last five years (2019-2023). Thus, we aimed to bibliometrically determine the position of the research topics in the literature.

Figure 1. Self-efficacy and work thematic map

If you look at the self-productivity and business theme map (figure 1) above, you can see that there are features that are briefly described below.

1. Niche theme (special theme)

Theme: "Engineering Education", "Curriculum", "Professional Aspects"

Analysis: These themes have a high degree of development (intensity), but the degree of their centrality (centrality) is low. This situation shows that these themes have been studied intensively in a specific specialty area, but not much attention has been paid to the general area.

2. Emerging or decreasing themes (emerging or decreasing themes)

Theme: "Survey", "Student e-learning"

Analysis: These themes have low values both in terms of centrality and degree of development. This indicates that these areas are still developing or are starting to lose interest.

3. Motor theme (main theme)

Theme: "Human", "human", "Self-concept"

Analysis: These themes have a high degree of centrality and development. This shows that these themes are the central and most dynamic topics in this field. Intensive research is being conducted on these themes, and the main developments in this field are shaped around these issues.

4. Basic Theme (Basic theme)

Theme: "Teaching", "Self-Efficacy", "Education", "Psychological aspects"

Analysis: These themes are more central, but have a lower degree of development. These themes form the basic building blocks of the field, but are not dynamically developed.

If you look at the Self-efficacy and alienation thematic map (figure 2), you can see that there are features that are briefly described below.

1. Niche theme (special theme)

Theme: "South Africa", "Condoms", "Alcohol consumption", "Alcoholism", "Anxiety disorder"

Analysis: These themes are very developed, but less centralized. This indicates a study that focuses on a specific region or a specific topic.

2. Emerging or decreasing themes (emerging or decreasing themes)

Theme: "Acceleration" "Clinical Psychology" "Consciousness"

Analysis: These themes have low values both in terms of centrality and degree of development. This indicates that these areas are just beginning to attract attention or are losing interest.

3. Motor theme (main theme)

Theme: "Elderly", "Psychological aspects", "Social isolation", "Middle age", "Large clinical trials", "Alienation"

Analysis: These themes have a high degree of centrality and development. These themes represent the central and most interesting topics in the field of research.

4. Basic Theme (Basic theme)

Theme: "Human", "human", "woman"

Analysis: These themes are more central, but have a lower degree of development. These themes represent the basic concepts of the field, but are not dynamically developed.

Figure 2. Self-efficacy and alienation thematic map

The analysis of Figures 1 and 2 above shows that a very different shape emerges as a thematic type map. While the theme "self-efficacy and work" has a strong educational and psychological dimension, the theme "self-efficacy and alienation" tends to have a strong behavioral and cultural component, as well as clinical research and case studies with middle-aged and older people.

Figure 3. Outstanding concepts and historical changes in academic research on self-efficacy and work in the Scopus index over the past five years (2019-2023).

As can be seen in Figure 3 above, it shows the evolution of research on education, self-efficacy, and related concepts from 1983 through 2023. This figure is divided into four main periods

1983-2013: this period focuses on 'human beings' and 'women'. This indicates a high level of interest in human factors in general and gender-oriented research in particular.

2014-2018: concepts such as 'teaching', 'students' and 'self-efficacy' come to the fore. Technological aspects of education (e.g. "engineering education") and new methodologies such as e-learning take center stage.

2019-2021: The focus here will be on "action research" and "middle age" groups. This shows that self-assessment and educational concepts still play an important role.

2022-2023: More recently, pandemic and quality of life issues such as "covid-19" and "quality of life" have entered the field of research.

Figure 4. Outstanding concepts and historical changes in academic research on self-efficacy and exclusion in the Scopus index over the past five years (2019-2023).

Analysis of Figure 4 above shows

1990-2012: the emphasis is on "large clinical studies" and "psychological aspects", with most studies conducted in the general population.

2013-2018: 'questionnaire survey' studies appear, with results used for psychological assessment.

2019-2021: During this period, more attention is paid to the categories of "women" and "adolescents". This indicates an increased focus on specific populations.

2022-2023: During this period, more in-depth and longer-term studies such as "longitudinal studies" become the focus.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 analyze the following

1- Changing research focus Figure 3 shows how research on education and self-esteem has evolved and expanded over time. Figure 4, on the other hand, highlights the changing nature of psychological and clinical research and how its focus has changed over time.

2. demographic and methodological changes: both figures illustrate how interest in demographic groups and research methodology has changed over time. Figure 3 shows the integration of technology into education (e.g., e-learning) and Figure 4 shows the increased interest in certain demographic groups (e.g., women and adolescents).

3. impact of the pandemic Figure 3 clearly shows the impact of COVID-19 on the research sector in 2022-2023. Therefore, studies have been conducted to investigate the impact of the pandemic on education and quality of life.

In the summary, it can be seen that there is no significant change in research on self-efficacy and alienation after 2019, while research on self-efficacy and work after 2019 has shifted to focus on learning and motivation.

Figure 5. Self-efficacy and work Factorial Analysis

Figure 5 shows that the concepts of self-efficacy, education and students are in close proximity to each other. This may suggest that self-efficacy has a close relationship with the educational process and student participation. Concepts such as 'health professionals' attitudes' and 'organization and management' are further away from the other concepts, suggesting that they are less relevant to students, education and self-efficacy in this particular dataset.

Figure 6 shows that the three concepts of alienation, self-efficacy and students are close to each other. This may indicate that student engagement and self-efficacy may determine teachers' sense of alienation. The slight separation between the concepts of consequences and learning may also indicate that these concepts are not directly related to feelings of alienation and self-efficacy.

Looking at Figures 5 and 6 together, it is clear that both figures emphasize the importance of the concepts of 'student', 'self-efficacy' and 'education', but the second figure focuses more on alienation. Figure 5 covers a broader range of concepts, while Figure 6 has a narrower focus and addresses a specific topic (alienation, self-efficacy) in more detail.

Figure 6. Self-efficacy and alienation

The differences between the two figures may reflect different aspects of the research questions and the dataset used. Figure 5 represents a broader perspective, while Figure 6 appears to take a more focused approach to testing specific hypotheses. Both figures demonstrate different perspectives on improving

the professional practice of teachers and educators. Such depictions may have important implications for education policy, curriculum design, and teacher preparation programs. Some of the factors that may contribute are summarized below:

1. Self-efficacy and student engagement: both graphs highlight the relationship between 'self-efficacy' and 'students'. Research shows that teacher self-efficacy has a significant impact on student achievement and classroom interaction. When teachers feel more confident in their abilities, they can plan more effective lessons, engage students, and create a more supportive learning environment. These graphs suggest that teacher education programs should focus on increasing teacher confidence.

2. alienation***: the close relationship between the concept of alienation and self-efficacy and students in Figure 6 suggests that important strategies need to be developed to increase teacher commitment and professional satisfaction. Reducing teachers' alienation can increase their professional efficacy and improve their relationship with students. This can be an important indicator for school authorities to provide teacher support programs and professional development opportunities.

3. Educational Policy and Curriculum Development An analysis of the variables in the graphs suggests that educational policies and curricula should be designed to promote student engagement and support teacher self-efficacy. In particular, the close relationship between the concepts of education and self-efficacy in Figure 5 suggests that educational strategies can have a direct impact on teacher self-efficacy.

4- Research and development: figures 5 and 6 also show how academic and educational research can contribute to teachers' professional development. In particular, multivariate models and studies of different groups of teachers can be used to develop more effective teaching strategies.

They can also be useful for educational administrators and policymakers in identifying ways to increase teacher job satisfaction, support student academic achievement, and improve the overall quality of education. In addition, teachers' continuous improvement of their professional practice can enable them to deliver more innovative and interactive lessons.

The above summarizes the position of the research topic in the general index of applications. The applications of this study are as follows. Descriptive statistics of the research are as follows:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Total Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage
0-5 years	43	13,2
6-10 years	81	24,8
11-15 years	82	25,2
16-20 years	71	21,8
20 years or more	49	15,0
Total	326	100,0

Job Title	Frequency	Percentage
Principal	17	5,2
Assistant Principal	21	6,4
Teacher	288	88,3
Total	326	100,0

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	250	76,7
Male	76	23,3
Total	326	100,0

Professional Experience	Frequency	Percentage
0-5 years	35	10,7
6-10 years	76	23,3
11-15 years	95	29,1
16-20 years	62	19,0
20 years or more	58	17,8
Total	326	100,0

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Age 20-29	40	12,3
Age 30-39	150	46,0
Age 40-49	109	33,4
Age 50-59	23	7,1
Age 60 or above	4	1,2
Total	326	100,0

Educational Field	Frequency	Percentage
Verbal Field	285	87,4

Numerical Field	41	12,6
Total	326	100,0

Table 1 indicates that 76.7% of participants are females and 23.3% of them are males, that 87.4% of participants have graduated from departments in verbal fields such as linguistics, history or social sciences whereas 12.6% of them have graduated from departments in numerical fields such as mathematics and sciences, that 58.3% of participants are lower than 40 years old and that 88.3% of them work as teachers.

Table 2: Results of Reliability Tests

Dimensions	Cronbach α
Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale – Student Participation	,856
Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale – Teaching Strategies	,864
Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale – Classroom Management	,902
Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale	,933
Work-Alienation Scale - Powerlessness	,877
Whole Questionnaire	,905

Since Cronbach α value is higher than .70 in all scales, all questionnaires are accepted as being valid and reliable.

Table 3: Model Summary of Regression Test

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
				R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
,245 ^a	,060	,031	,687	,060	2,063	3	97	,036	1,873

a. Predictors: (Constant), Classroom Management, Student Participation, Teaching Strategies

b. Dependent Variable: Powerlessness

Durbin Watson Statistic searches for whether there is correlation between error terms or not. This statistic goes between 0 and 4. If statistic value is approximate to 2, that means there is no correlation. Values close to 0 means high positive correlation and values close to 4 implies high negative correlation. Durbin Watson Statistic value in the table above is 1.873. Therefore, there is no correlation between error terms in our model.

Table 4: Regression Analysis for Determining the Effect of Teacher Self-Efficacy on Powerlessness Dimension of Work Alienation

Variables	B	t	p	F	Sig.F	Collinearity Statistics	
						Tolerance	VIF
Constant	2,084	3,294	,001	2,063	,036		
Student participation	-,247	-2,090	,039			,644	1,554
Teaching strategies	,068	,462	,645			,448	2,231
Classroom management	,215	1,522	,131			,501	1,996

Dependent Variable: Powerlessness

One of the main reasons for doing regression analysis is to make estimations about the future. For this to be, mathematical regression model must be significant. The table above shows that student participation has an influence on powerlessness dimension of work alienation and that regression formula for this influence can be written as $Y_{(\text{powerlessness})} = 2.084 - 0.247_{(\text{student participation})}$

As Table 4 indicates, collinearity statistics for student participation is approximately 1.554. It can be claimed that there is no correlation between variables since the value is not 5 or more than 5

and that other variables can also remain in the model. However, they are not included in the regression formula since their p values are bigger than .050.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to research data, it was concluded that student participation, which is a dimension of teacher self-efficacy scale, affects powerlessness dimension of teachers' alienation to work. The fact that students contributing proactively to the class strengthen the perceptions of teachers, who feels themselves alienated to work, that they do not lose the control of classroom can be effective in this outcome.

Institutions should actively ensure that educators spend time teaching basic life skills as well as academic knowledge (Chen, 2024: 10). When focusing on teachers' mental well-being, there are several factors to consider. For example, teachers should be provided with evidence-based programs implemented at the institutional level to provide professional safeguards and well-developed systems and positive drivers that are important for fostering self-efficacy (Guoyan et al, 2023).

Educational institutions need to ensure that educators are actively spending time teaching basic life skills as well as academic knowledge. When it comes to teacher mental health, there are many factors to consider. For example, evidence-based programs, well-developed systems implemented at the organizational level, and positive reinforcement must be provided, which is important to increase teacher self-efficacy.

In the literature, general self-efficacy has been studied in the context of similar variables and groups such as university students and teachers, but multidimensional issues such as job alienation, with scales developed for specific groups such as teachers, have received little attention. Creating multivariate research models, examining different groups or samples for their perceptions of self-efficacy and comparing them could make a positive contribution to the literature.

We therefore offer the following recommendations:

1. Educational policies should be organized to support teachers in developing ways to increase student engagement.
2. Educational institutions can enhance teachers' self-efficacy and detachment by providing continuing education programs for their professional development.
3. Academic research should further explore multidimensional issues such as work alienation. In particular, focusing on specific groups, such as teachers, will allow for the development of solutions that address the specific needs and concerns of these groups.
4. A long-term study of teachers is needed to examine in detail the relationship between self-efficacy and job alienation.

These recommendations will be effective in reducing teachers' feelings of alienation from their work and increasing their self-efficacy.

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